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Interpersonal Sexual Objectification Experiences: Psychological and Social Well-Being Consequences for Women

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Abstract

Sexual objectification as a form of sexist discrimination accounts for the higher prevalence of psychological problems among women. More specifically, sexual objectification manifests itself in different ways with different intensities, in turn affecting women's psychological well-being differently. On one hand, experiences of body evaluation are more subtle and work by perpetuating sexist attitudes among women themselves. On the other hand, more explicit forms of sexual objectification (unwanted explicit sexual advances) are linked to higher levels of anxiety and lower levels of self-esteem. The first study, on a sample of 343 Spanish women, aims to analyze the consequences of different forms of sexual objectification on women's psychological well-being and the effect of sexism and enjoyment of objectification on these consequences. The second study, on a sample of 144 Spanish women, focuses on analyzing the ideological variables that have an effect on response to acts of sexist discrimination. Both studies reveal the significance of the more subtle experiences of sexual objectification as a mechanism that plays a part in keeping women in a subordinate position, where they end up feeling that this process is positive or pleasing.

Keywords

Sexual objectification, enjoyment of sexualization, benevolent sexism, self-silencing, sexuality

Although we tend to think that sexist discrimination is a thing of the past, empirical evidence shows that women today continue to be the object of constant discrimination on a daily basis (Swim, Hyers, Cohen, & Ferguson, 2001). One of the most widespread forms of discrimination against women is treating them as mere sexual objects to be looked at and evaluated on the basis of their physical appearance, ignoring their needs and wishes (Fredrickson & Roberts, 1997). It is a discriminatory interaction and a clear example of gender inequality when, in an interpersonal context, the interaction between a man and a woman is based on treating her as a sexual object, even going so far as to consider her body as the possession of the observer (Calogero, 2013).

These types of discriminatory interactions are termed *sexual objectification experiences* and are understood as the act of separating the sexual parts from the rest of the woman's body and personality, turning her into a tool and reducing her to these sexual parts (Bartky, 1990). Fredrickson and Roberts (1997) posit the objectification theory as the theory framework for understanding how gender socialization and sexual objectification experiences affect women's physical, psychological, and social well-being, establishing as pivotal in this theory the huge presence of sexual

objectification events in women's everyday lives. According to this theory, there are different forms of sexual objectification, which can be classified along a continuum, ranging from the more subtle (body evaluation) to the more extreme (unwanted explicit sexual advances; Fredrickson & Roberts, 1997). *Body evaluation* is the action of observing and analyzing a woman's body or body parts, whereas *unwanted explicit sexual advances* are sexual approaches made against a woman's wishes (Kozee, Tylka, Augustus-Horvath, & Denchik, 2007).

The distinction between both forms of sexual objectification is extremely relevant from both theoretical and applied perspectives. Unwanted explicit sexual advances are closely linked to certain types of sexual harassment (e.g., unwanted sexual attention, sexual assault, or sexual coercion) described in the literature, highly prevalent in society (Pina, Gannon, & Saunders, 2009) and with serious psychological consequences on the women who suffer them (Flack et al., 2015). And furthermore, continuous female body evaluation leading to assessment of women purely on the basis of their physical appearance makes it difficult for women to receive fair and equal treatment, because a different set of capabilities and skills are taken into account for women than for men (Heflick, Goldenberg, Cooper, & Puvia, 2011). The consequences of sexual objectification can be grouped into the ideological (e.g., benevolent sexism and enjoyment of sexualization), which are associated with women's legitimizing or rejecting these types of conduct and which affect interpersonal relationships, and the psychological (e.g., anxiety and self-esteem), which clearly have an effect on women's well-being.

Ideological Correlates of Sexual Objectification: Benevolent Sexism and Enjoyment of Sexualization

Sexist ideology is closely linked to the phenomenon of sexual objectification (Riemer, Chaudoir, & Earnshaw, 2014). Sexism is understood as an attitude toward persons formed on the basis of their biological sex (Expósito, Moya, & Glick, 1998). The importance of the sexist ideology is due to the link between negative attitudes toward women and violence against them (Beck, Boys, Rose, & Beck, 2012). With regard to sexism, a theory of particular relevance is the *theory of ambivalent sexism* (Glick & Fiske, 1996), which states that ambivalence in prejudice against women is due to positive feelings toward women coexisting with hostile dislike of women. Ambivalent sexism is therefore the combination of the more traditional type of sexism (hostile sexism) and sexism with a markedly positive bent (benevolent sexism; Glick & Fiske, 1996). Hostile sexism essentially refers to the traditional sexism. However, benevolent sexism is described as a set of interrelated attitudes toward women that are sexist in that they regard women in a stereotypical way, yet with a tone of positive affect (for the perceiver). Benevolent sexism tends to inspire in the perceiver behaviors, which are typically categorized as prosocial (e.g., help) or the quest for intimacy (Glick & Fiske, 1996).

Women's responses toward a male perpetrator depend on the sexist ideology attributed to him (Durán, Moya, & Megías, 2014) and on their own sexist ideology assimilation. That women themselves subscribe to sexist ideology can be explained by the social rewards benevolent sexism offers to women who conform to socially expected norms and who do not pose a threat to the male status quo (Glick & Fiske, 1996). One of the principal areas in which women are rewarded is in relation to physical appearance; so physical attractiveness becomes a tool, which women can use to obtain certain social advantages (Fiske, Bersoff, Borgida, Deaux, & Heilman, 1991). The body evaluation inherent in sexual objectification experiences has a bearing on women's

preoccupation with how they look. This preoccupation is associated with seeking social rewards, which are fostered by sexist ideology. Specifically, Franzoi (2001) demonstrates the existence of the link between stronger subscription to sexist ideology and greater preoccupation with appearance.

The fact that women receive social rewards for their physical appearance means that in certain situations, some women enjoy sexual objectification experiences and do not perceive them as something negative (Liss, Erchull, & Ramsey, 2011). Enjoyment of sexualization occurs when a woman finds sexual attention based on her appearance to be pleasing. There is empirical evidence of the relationship between enjoyment of sexualization and more benevolent sexist ideology (Sáez, Valor-Segura, & Expósito, 2012), which results in women who enjoy sexual self-objectification being more influenced by the rewards of benevolent sexism.

Consequences on Psychological Well-Being: Higher Levels of Anxiety and Lower Levels of Self-Esteem

Regarding the psychological consequences, repeated exposure to sexual objectification experiences is linked to low self-esteem and high levels of anxiety, which affect women's psychological well-being (Klonoff & Landrine, 1995). Miles-McLean et al. (2015) describe the link between sexual objectification experiences and trauma symptoms.

The impact of sexual objectification experiences on self-esteem can depend on the extremeness of such experiences (Moffitt & Szymanski, 2011). More subtle experiences of objectification, the kind that evaluate women's bodies and physical attractiveness, could, in the short term, increase the self-esteem of women who assess objectification experiences more positively, although in the long term, these levels of self-esteem will not be maintained (Breines, Crocker, & Garcia, 2008). By contrast, more extreme experiences of sexual objectification such as unwanted explicit sexual advances can be invasive enough to have a direct impact on women's self-esteem, damaging them deeply and permanently (Polce-Lynch, Myers, Kliever, & Kilmartin, 2001).

Exposure to acts of sexual objectification is also linked to higher levels of anxiety (Lozano, Valor-Segura, Sáez, & Expósito, 2015). More extreme experiences of sexual objectification, such as unwanted explicit sexual advances, could increase the anxiety felt by the woman concerned as she perceives it as a threat to her safety (Szymanski, Moffitt, & Carr, 2011). Similarly, Fredrickson and Roberts (1997) describe how the continuous exposure to sexual objectification to which women are subjected causes them to exercise greater body monitoring, with the resultant increase in anxiety levels (Noll & Fredrickson, 1998).

Response to Sexual Objectification Experiences: Self-Silencing

Body evaluation refers to the evaluation of a woman's physique that can lead her to internalize this external evaluation and make it her own, which has come to be termed *self-objectification* (Fredrickson & Roberts, 1997). It triggers a process of self-monitoring, which leads to the comparison of the result of this evaluation with a beauty canon, which is sometimes unattainable. This continuous comparison with a culturally prescribed beauty norm is a key element for understanding why some women do not speak out against acts of sexist discrimination such as objectification (Jack, 2011). Women who, as a consequence of these comparisons, feel inferior tend to silence

their feelings and suffer increased levels of depression (Flett, Besser, Hewitt, & Davis, 2007), associated with these women's lower confrontational response to acts of sexist discrimination. By contrast, women who do conform to social norms and receive the social rewards offered for their physical appearance enjoy experiences of sexual objectification, and because they do not perceive them as something negative (Liss et al., 2011), nor do they confront the act of sexist discrimination of which they are the object.

Although it is healthier actively to confront any act of discrimination, the empirical evidence suggests that many women do not object to the sexist incidents they face almost every day of their lives (Swim, Eyssell, Murdoch, & Ferguson, 2010). The relational-cultural theory set out by Miller (1986a) provides the theory framework for explaining why women censure their thoughts and feelings when faced with an act of sexist discrimination. Miller (1986b) claims that humans develop through establishing and maintaining social relationships. During their socialization process, women in particular learn the importance of maintaining relationships with men, and so, when faced with negative or discriminatory situations, they deploy tactics termed "disconnection" strategies to preserve these relationships (Jordan, 2010).

Self-silencing is one such disconnection strategy used to maintain relationships, which are important for people (Jack, 1999). Self-silencing of thoughts and feelings represents the degree to which a person keeps his or her thoughts and opinions about something to himself or herself, instead of expressing his or her views. Individual opinion is self-censored in the interest of maintaining the relationship (Jack, 1991). The difference in gender socialization plays an important role in self-silencing when facing acts of sexual discrimination; women are socialized to adapt their behavior to what is expected of them and keep their thoughts, feelings, and opinions to themselves to nurture and maintain their relationships with men (Jack, 2011).

On the basis of the above considerations, sexual objectification interactions are scenarios that cause ambivalent feelings among women, because although these types of behavior constitute sexist discrimination, they also provide social advantages and turn sexist acts that should be repulsive into something pleasing (Liss et al., 2011). Enjoyment of how men sexualize women's bodies could determine how women respond to acts of sexual objectification.

As it has been said above, forms of sexual objectification vary in their intensity (Kooze et al., 2007) and predictably in their impact on women's psychological well-being. By means of two studies, this research carries out differential analysis of different types of sexual objectification experiences to determine the psychological consequences of different forms of sexual objectification more exhaustively, analyzing the impact of sexist ideology on these consequences and determining the factors that have an effect on confronting situations of sexist discrimination. The aim of the first study is to analyze the consequences of different forms of sexual objectification on psychological well-being among women (anxiety and self-esteem) and the effect of sexist ideology and enjoyment of sexualization on these consequences. The second study focuses on the effect of benevolent sexist ideology and enjoyment of sexualization on women's response to more subtle acts of sexist discrimination (experiences of body evaluation).

Study 1

The first hypothesis predicts that there will be a positive relationship between unwanted explicit sexual advances and higher anxiety, and a negative relationship with self-esteem (Hypothesis 1). By contrast, the second hypothesis predicts that among women who

subscribe to benevolent sexism, there will be a negative relationship between body evaluation and anxiety levels (Hypothesis 2). The third hypothesis predicts that among women who enjoy sexualization, there will be a positive relationship between reporting more experiences of sexual objectification and higher levels of self-esteem (Hypothesis 3).

Method

Participants. The sample comprises a total of 343 women recruited from the general population, with ages ranging from 18 to 62 years and a mean age of 24.17 years ($SD = 7.99$). Inclusion criteria for the final sample were being Spanish and of heterosexual orientation. Two point three percent of the participants have a basic education, 5.8% have secondary or vocational training, 4.1% graduated from high school, and 87.2% have college degrees. In addition, 0.3% of the participants reported having no basic education, and another 0.3% did not answer this question. The distribution of the sample by age showed that 77.6 % of the participants are between 18 and 24 years old, 12.2% are between 25 and 34, 5.5% are between 35 and 46 years old, and the remaining 4.7% are older.

Procedure and design. Participants were recruited by means of convenience sampling carried out in the city of Granada (Spain). Two previously trained researchers asked participants to take part, informing them that their replies would be kept anonymous and guaranteeing their confidentiality. The study design is correlational, as per the classification set out by Montero and León (2007).

Instruments. A questionnaire was constructed and included the following measures:

Sociodemographic characteristics. Data were collected on participant sex, age, nationality, educational attainment, and sexual orientation.

Interpersonal Sexual Objectification Scale (ISOS; Lozano et al., 2015). This contains 15 items, which evaluate interpersonal sexual objectification, and comprises two dimensions: *body evaluation* (11 items; e.g., “How often have you felt that someone is staring at your body?”) and *unwanted explicit sexual advances* (four items; e.g., “How often have you been groped?”). The answer format is a Likert-type scale of five answer options ranging from 1 (*never*) to 5 (*almost always*). The scale has good reliability in this sample, with a Cronbach’s alpha of .87 and .76 for the sub-scales of Body Evaluation and Unwanted Explicit Sexual Advances, respectively.

Enjoyment of Sexualization Scale (ESS; Liss et al., 2011). To adapt it to Spanish, the original scale was translated and back-translated. It contains eight items evaluating enjoyment of sexualization in an interpersonal context (e.g., “I like to feel sexy”). The answer format is a Likert-type scale ranging from 1 (*totally disagree*) to 6 (*totally agree*). The internal consistency in this sample was .86, similar to that obtained by Liss et al. (2011), which was .87.

Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (RSES; Rosenberg, 1965). This is a self-esteem measure with 10 items evaluating a person’s degree of satisfaction with himself or herself (e.g., “I am able to do things as well as anybody else”). The answer format is a Likert-type scale ranging from 1 (*totally disagree*) to 4 (*totally agree*). Internal consistency of the

original scale is between .76 and .87, showing a Cronbach's alpha coefficient in this study of .83.

Table 1. Mean Scores, Standard Deviation, and Correlations Between Variables (Study 1).

	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	Range	1	2	3	4	5
1. Body evaluation	2.49	0.57	1-5	—				
2. Unwanted sexual advances	1.34	0.47	1-5	.47***	—			
3. Enjoyment of sexualization	3.35	0.99	1-7	.42***	.20***	—		
4. Benevolent sexism	1.41	0.91	0-5	.16**	.06	.26***	—	
5. Self-esteem	32.78	4.72	10-40	.07	-.07	.03	.11*	—
6. Anxiety	16.84	9.37	0-60	-.02	.13*	.07	.14**	-.50**

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$.

State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI; Spielberger, Gorsuch, & Lushene, 1982) In accordance with the research objectives, the State-trait Anxiety Scale from this questionnaire was used. The scale has 20 items and a 4-point Likert-type answer scale (e.g., “I feel uneasy”) and an internal consistency for the sample of .91.

Ambivalent Sexism Inventory (Expósito et al., 1998). This has 22 items and a Likert-type answer format ranging from 0 (*totally disagree*) to 5 (*totally agree*). This study used the Benevolent Sexism sub-scale containing 11 items (e.g., “women must be loved and protected by men”). In this study, the Benevolent Sexism sub-scale obtained a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of .86.

Results

Preliminary results. As can be observed in Table 1, scores for the body evaluation dimension correlated positively with benevolent sexist ideology ($r = .16, p = .003$) and enjoyment of sexualization ($r = .42, p < .001$), whereas more extreme experiences of objectification related positively with levels of anxiety ($r = .13, p = .018$) and greater enjoyment of sexualization ($r = .20, p < .001$).

The effect of sexual objectification, enjoyment of sexualization, and benevolent sexism on psychological consequences (anxiety and self-esteem). Independent regression analyses were performed to analyze the effect of different types of sexual objectification experiences (body evaluation and unwanted explicit sexual advances) on women's well-being (anxiety and self-esteem). The results revealed that more extreme experiences of sexual objectification (unwanted explicit sexual advances) predicted the level of anxiety felt by

Table 2. The Effect of Sexual Objectification (Body Evaluation) and Benevolent Sexism on anxiety (Study 1).

Variables	β	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
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Step 1			
ISOS (Eva)	-.05	-.875	.38
Benevolent sexism	.15	2.79	.006
R^2	.02		
Step 2			
ISOS (Eva) × Benevolent sexism	-.17	-3.12	.002
ΔR^2	.05		

Note. ISOS (Eva) = Body evaluation; ISOS = Interpersonal Sexual Objectification Scale.

Figure 1. Interaction between body evaluation and benevolent sexism in anxiety (Study 1).

women ($\beta = .13$, $p = .02$), although the negative impact that sexual advances had on self-esteem was not significant ($\beta = -.07$, $p = .20$). From this, we might conclude that the first hypothesis is partially fulfilled.

To test the second hypothesis regarding the effect of benevolent sexism and body evaluation on anxiety levels among women, hierarchical regression analysis was performed taking the anxiety score as criterion variable, and as predictor variables, benevolent sexism of participants and body evaluation were introduced in Step 1 and the interaction between both variables in Step 2. As can be observed in Table 2, results revealed the main effect of benevolent sexism on anxiety, $t(342) = 2.79$, $\beta = .15$, $p = .006$, benevolent sexism thus predicting higher anxiety levels. In turn, results revealed significant interaction between body evaluation and benevolent sexism,

Table 3. The Effect of Sexual Objectification (Body Evaluation) and Enjoyment of Sexualization on Self-Esteem (Study 1).

Variables	β	t	P
Step 1			
ISOS (Eva)	.07	1.23	.22
Enjoyment of sexualization	-.001	-0.02	.99
R^2	.005		
Step 2			
ISOS (Eva) × Enjoyment of sexualization	.10	1.86	.06
ΔR^2	.015		

Note. ISOS (Eva) = Body evaluation; ISOS = Interpersonal Sexual Objectification Scale.

Figure 2. Interaction between enjoyment of sexualization and benevolent sexism in self-esteem (Study 1).

$t(342) = -3.12$, $\beta = -.17$, $p = .002$ (see Figure 1). That is to say, among participants who scored highly in benevolent sexism, reporting low body evaluation was related to higher levels of anxiety. Among women who do not subscribe strongly to benevolent sexist ideology, no relationship was observed between body evaluation and levels of anxiety.

In order to test the prediction that the effect of enjoyment of sexualization and body evaluation on self-esteem levels (Hypothesis 3), hierarchical regression analysis was performed. Self-esteem was taken as criterion variable, and body evaluation and enjoyment of sexualization as predictor variables were introduced in step 1, and the interaction between body evaluation and enjoyment of sexualization in step 2. Results did not reveal main effects either of body evaluation or of enjoyment of sexualization on levels of self-esteem. However, as Figure 2 shows, there is a marginally significant interaction between body evaluation and enjoyment of sexualization in self-esteem, $t(342) = 1.86$, $\beta = .10$, $p = .06$ (see Table 3). That is to say, only among women who scored highly in enjoyment of sexualization, high body evaluation was related to higher self-esteem. Among women with low enjoyment of sexualization, this effect was not significant.

In sum, the results of this study showed the relationship between exposure to extreme sexual objectification (unwanted explicit sexual advances) and higher levels of anxiety. In spite of the negative impact that more extreme experiences of sexual objectification have on anxiety among women, the results revealed that women scored highly in benevolent sexism and had higher levels of anxiety if their experiences of body evaluation were fewer. Moreover, among women who enjoy their own sexualization, it was found that the more subtle experiences of sexual objectification had a positive impact on their self-esteem.

Study 2

The results of the first study showed that experiences of sexual objectification had a psychological impact on women, and that in the more subtle forms of sexual objectification, benevolent sexist ideology and enjoyment of sexualization played a more significant role.

The aim of the second study was therefore to verify the role that sexist ideology plays in women's response to sexist discrimination. Specifically, benevolent sexism was predicted to explain the link between women reporting a higher number of body evaluation experiences and more self-silencing when faced with sexist discrimination (Hypothesis 4). Benevolent sexism was also predicted to explain the link between enjoyment of sexualization and self-silencing when facing sexist discrimination (Hypothesis 5).

Method

Participants. The sample comprises a total of 144 women recruited from the general population, with ages ranging from 18 to 54 years and a mean age of 25.14 years ($SD = 7.7$). Inclusion criteria for the final sample were being Spanish and of heterosexual orientation. One point four percent of the participants have a basic education, other 1.4% reported having no basic education, 20.2% had secondary or vocational training, 10.4% graduated from high school, and 66 % had college degrees. In addition, one woman did not provide her educational degree. Regarding the distribution of the sample by age, 62.5 % were between 18 and 24 years, 26.4% were between 25 and 34 years, 5.6% were between 35 and 44 years, and the remaining 4.9% were above 45 years. In addition, one woman did not provide her age.

Procedure and design. Participants were recruited by means of convenience sampling carried out in the city of Granada (Spain). A previously trained researcher went to the bus station and asked participants to take part, informing them that their replies would be kept anonymous and guaranteeing their confidentiality. The study design was correlational, as per the classification set out by Montero and León (2007).

Instruments

Sociodemographic characteristics. Data were collected on participant sex, age, nationality, educational attainment, and sexual orientation.

ISOS (Lozano et al., 2015). It has been described in study 1, in this study reliability was demonstrated with a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of .83 and .77 for the sub-scales of body evaluation and unwanted explicit sexual advances, respectively.

ESS (Liss et al., 2011). The internal consistency in this study was .86.

ASI (Expósito et al., 1998). The benevolent sexism dimension was used in this study, and a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of .86 was obtained.

The Silencing the Self Scale (STSS; Jack & Dill, 1992). Adapted to Spanish for this study by translation and back-translation this scale contains 31 items (e.g., "I tend to judge myself in terms of how I think other people see me," "I don't talk about my feelings in a relationship when I know they will cause disagreement"). The answer format was a Likert-type scale ranging from 1 (*totally disagree*) to 5 (*totally agree*). Internal consistency of the scale for this sample was .82, similar to that obtained by Hurst and Beesley (2013).

Results

As can be seen in Table 4, scores in body evaluation marginally correlated significantly and positively with self-silencing (STSS), so that participants who perceive more body evaluation in their everyday lives were more self-silencing with regard to their thoughts and feelings ($r = .16, p = .07$). STSS scores also correlated positively and significantly with enjoyment of

Table 4. Mean Scores, Standard Deviation, and Correlations Between Variables (Study 2).

	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	Range	1	2	3
1. Body evaluation	2.52	0.51	1-5	—		
2. Enjoyment of sexualization	3.39	1.00	1-7	.34***	—	
3. Benevolent sexism	1.71	1.00	0-5	.26**	.23**	—
4. Self-silencing	74.18	17.20	31-155	.16 [†]	.20*	.44***

[†] $p = .07$. * $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$. *** $p < .001$.

sexualization (ESS; $r = .20, p = .02$), so that participants who enjoy sexualization were more self-silencing with regard to their thoughts and feelings. Moreover, self-silencing (STSS) related positively and significantly to benevolent sexism ($r = .44, p < .001$), so that the women who subscribe to a more benevolent sexist ideology were more prone to keep their thoughts to themselves in a sexualized context.

Benevolent sexism as mediator in the relationship between body evaluation and self-silencing. To verify the mediating effect of benevolent sexism in the relationship between body evaluation and self-silencing (Hypothesis 4), a mediation analysis was carried out using PROCESS (Hayes, 2013). In the proposed model, the effect of body evaluation (ISOS Eva) is the predictor variable (X), self-silencing is the criteria variable (Y), and benevolent sexism the mediator (M). Using the recommendations of MacKinnon, Lockwood, and Williams (2004), non-parametric bootstrapping with 5,000 repetitions to calculate the 95% confidence intervals (CI) was used. Bootstrapping determines whether the indirect effect of mediators differs significantly from zero. If the confidence interval of the indirect effect does not include 0, the indirect effect is significant and, therefore, mediation can be said to exist. To do this, the SPSS macro provided by Hayes and Preacher (2014) was used.

As can be observed in Table 5, the analysis showed that the indirect effect of the ISOS Eva on the self-silencing through benevolent sexism was 3.76, 95% CI = [1.02, 7.47]. Because these intervals do not include zero, the findings suggested that the indirect effect of benevolent sexism was significant, indicating mediation of benevolent sexism in the relationship between body evaluation and self-silencing (Figure 3).

Benevolent sexism as mediator in the relationship between enjoyment of sexualization and self-silencing. To verify the mediating effect of benevolent sexism in the relationship between enjoyment of sexualization and self-silencing (Hypothesis 5), a mediation analysis was carried out using PROCESS (Hayes, 2013). In the proposed model, the effect of enjoyment of

Table 5. Regression Coefficients, Standard Errors, and Summary of Information in Mediation Model in Figure 3 (Study 2).

Antecedent	Consequent
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	M ₁ (Benevolent Sexism)			Y (Self-Silencing)		
	Coefficient	SE	p	Coefficient	SE	P
X (Body evaluation)	0.53	0.17	.002	1.40	2.69	.60
M ₁ (Benevolent sexism)	—	—	—	7.16	1.493	<.001
Constant	0.40	0.42	.35	58.04	6.67	<.001
	$R^2 = .08$			$R^2 = .20$		
	$F(1, 121) = 10.11, p = .002$			$F(2, 120) = 14.61, p < .001$		

Figure 3. The mediating effect of benevolent sexism in the relationship between body evaluation and self-silencing (Study 2).

sexualization (ESS) is the predictor variable (X), self-silencing is the criteria variable (Y), and benevolent sexism the mediator (M). To analyze benevolent sexism mediation, the recommendations of MacKinnon et al. (2004) mentioned above were followed, and the same procedure used (Hayes & Preacher, 2014).

As can be observed in Table 6, The analysis showed that the indirect effect of the enjoyment of sexualization on the self-silencing through benevolent sexism was 1.40, 95% LC = [0.39, 2.93]. Because these intervals do not include zero, the findings suggested that the indirect effect of benevolent sexism was significant, indicating mediation of benevolent sexism in the relationship between enjoyment of sexualization and self-silencing (Figure 4).

The results of Study 2 revealed the relationship between higher exposure to body evaluation, higher subscription to benevolent sexist ideology, higher enjoyment of sexualization, and higher censure of themselves in sexist discrimination. The first mediation analysis showed how benevolent sexism totally mediated the relationship between more experiences of body evaluation and self-silencing when faced with sexist discrimination. The

Table 6. Regression Coefficients, Standard Errors, and Summary of Information in Mediation Model in Figure 4 (Study 2).

Antecedent	Consequent					
	M (Benevolent Sexism)			Y (Self-Silencing)		
	Coefficient	SE	p	Coefficient	SE	p
X (Enjoyment of sexualization)	0.20	0.09	.022	1.89	1.35	.16
M (Benevolent sexism)	—	—	—	6.96	1.35	<.001
Constant	1.04	0.31	<.001	55.49	4.88	<.001

$$R^2 = .04$$
$$F(1, 121) = 5.39, p = .02$$

$$R^2 = .21$$
$$F(2, 120) = 15.66, p < .001$$

Figure 4. The mediating effect of benevolent sexism in the relationship between enjoyment of sexualization and self-silencing (Study 2).

second mediation analysis showed how benevolent sexism also accounted for the relationship between enjoyment of sexualization and women keeping their thoughts and feelings to themselves.

In line with these results, it is the more subtle forms of sexual objectification, which some women enjoy, that have a bearing on these women being less proactive and more self-silencing in their social relationships with men (Saguy, Quinn, Dovidio, & Pratto, 2010), and this appears to be due to their subscribing more strongly to the benevolent sexist ideology, which justifies and legitimizes gender inequality.

General Discussion

We live in a heteronormative society (e.g., a society that promotes heterosexuality as the “normal” or preferred orientation) where the practice of female body objectification is omnipresent (Fredrickson & Roberts, 1997). There are many forms of sexual objectification, which differ in their extremity and in their repercussions on women’s well-being.

The consequences on female psychological well-being of the most extreme forms of sexual objectification (unwanted explicit sexual advances) are similar to those of other forms of sexism (Klonoff, Landrine, & Campbell, 2000). By contrast, some women find discrimination in the guise of the more subtle forms of sexual objectification (female body evaluation) desirable in their interaction with men (Murnen & Smolak, 2012). The results of this study showed that although body evaluation is not linked to indicators of psychological distress, it is linked to the ideology that legitimizes the perpetuation of this type of behavior. The significance of sexist ideology is such that women with higher benevolent sexism scores experience lower anxiety levels when exposed to a higher number of body evaluation experiences; similarly, women who enjoy sexualization find their self-esteem is boosted the more experiences of body evaluation they report. Notwithstanding the results obtained, more exhaustive analysis is required of the apparently positive impact of the more subtle experiences of sexual objectification on self-image and anxiety among certain women. The empirical evidence warns that the enjoyment of objectifying experiences cannot be considered a protective factor against the harmful psychological consequences of sexual objectification (Liss et al., 2011).

Regarding the impact of the objectification phenomenon on women’s social relationships, benevolent sexism also plays a decisive role. The significance of benevolent sexism as a variable accounting for self-silencing in acts of discrimination

and enjoyment of sexualization can be explained by how women themselves interpret different experiences of sexual objectification as a form of sexist discrimination, justifying them and considering them as something empowering, which leads them not to confront such situations (Becker & Wright, 2011). This process distils the essence of sexist benevolent ideology, in the sense that women are admired and desired by men, and this gives them feelings of pleasure, causing them to keep their thoughts and feelings to themselves not to jeopardize the social relationships they value (Jack, 2011). Benevolent sexism has been closely related to the level of gender inequality (Glick et al., 2000). It has to be considered that the samples of the studies have been recollected in Spain. This country has a .095 score in the Gender Inequality Index (GII), and it is ranked in the 16th position of the countries with more gender equality around the world (Jahan, 2015).

The results of both studies taken together demonstrate the complex and ambivalent nature of female sexual objectification and, in particular, highlight ideological variables such as benevolent sexism and enjoyment of sexualization, which are closely linked to each other. Regarding enjoyment of sexualization, on one hand, it might be considered an empowerment strategy deployed by women through their sexuality (Baumgardner & Richards, 2004). On the other hand, this enjoyment is associated with more strongly subscribing to a benevolent sexist ideology, which perpetuates the position of women as inferior to and dependent on men; so it is more a manifestation of false, not true, empowerment (Levy, 2005), leading women to practice self-silencing to a greater degree and happily accept their subordinate position.

Although the present work provides evidence for the psychological and social consequences of sexual objectification, it is important to consider the role of individual characteristics and cultural context in the sexual objectification phenomenon (Loughnan et al., 2015). Culture is central to sexual objectification, because the “bodies exist within social and cultural contexts, and hence are also constructed through sociocultural practices and discourses” (Fredrickson & Roberts, 1997, p. 174). The samples of the current studies were composed by Western women, being that sexual objectification is more prevalent in this culture and could be associated with more personal and social consequences of objectification for women than non-Western culture (Loughnan et al., 2015). However, the age of the woman is a key individual variable in the study of the consequences of sexual objectification experiences (McKinley, 2011). The different biological stages of a woman’s life may create a differential risk of higher sexual objectification (McKinley, 2011). It must be considered that the sample of the present studies corresponds to the period from puberty to early adulthood when women fully manifest an objectified view of themselves (Fredrickson & Roberts, 1997; McKinley, 2011). Therefore, for futures studies, it may be important to include women from different ages and different cultures.

Practical Implications

The aim of these studies had been to contribute to a better understanding of how the more subtle forms of sexual objectification operate. The more explicit forms of sexist discrimination are easy to identify and reject, but it is in the more subtle forms of sexist discrimination (looking at women’s bodies, compliments on appearance) where women find themselves having to negotiate their way through a labyrinth of social rewards in exchange for not confronting sexist discrimination. Thus, once women have learnt to silence their thoughts and feelings in return for having their beauty valued by men, it is difficult to tackle something more serious, such as explicit sexual harassment, effectively. The results of these studies are extremely useful for promoting mental

health and in early action programs with girls and young women, where they need to be taught to recognize body evaluation experiences as acts of sexist discrimination and prevent them from associating this kind of discrimination with gaining social rewards, so that they learn actively to confront it.

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